

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

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NATIONAL VALUES IN S. S. AXUNDOV'S SHORT STORY "QARACA GIRL"

Abstract

Written in 1913 and published in the journal *Məktəb*, S. S. Akhundov's short story *Qaraca qız* explores important moral and educational themes. The narrative presents instructive events and human destinies that serve to deepen the reader's understanding of life.

There are two versions of the story. In the first version, Hüseyinqulu Agha and Pəricahan Khanum are profoundly affected by *Qaraca Girl*'s self-sacrifice. They consider themselves responsible for her death and pray to God for the forgiveness of their sins.

The second version, which was included for many years in general education "Literature" textbooks, reflects the changes the author was compelled to make in 1936 while preparing his collected works for publication. Anticipating the wave of repression in 1937, the writer made omissions and alterations to shield himself from impending danger. He recast Hüseyinqulu Agha and Pəricahan Khanum, who belong to the wealthy landowning class, as negative figures. The original version was later published in *Hikmət çələngi* (Baku, 1997), compiled by X. Mammadov.

In the story, *Qaraca Girl*, who loses her parents during an earthquake, manages to preserve her purity and natural kindness despite the injustices she faces in life. The death of her foster mother Yasaman in the river, Yusuf's cruelty, and the deprivation she endures in Hüseyinqulu Agha's household all place her under severe trials. Yet she remains steadfast. She lives with trust and affection for those around her, and is remembered for her cheerful and spirited character, optimism, warmth, compassion, and sincerity.

Qaraca qız is a folkloric narrative written with high artistic skill. Its success lies in its coherent plot, the logical progression of events, the vivid and natural descriptions, and its realism. The story makes effective use of language, expressions, and a narrative style reminiscent of traditional fairy tales.

Keywords: child, national value, orphan, *Qaraca Girl*, S. S. Akhundov, short story.

Süleyman Sani Akhundov is recognized in the history of Azerbaijani literature as a prose writer, playwright, and a figure of enlightenment and culture. His dramatic works and stories, particularly the *Fearful Tales* series, have been repeatedly published and have earned great affection from readers. *Qaraca Girl*, which is part of the *Fearful Tales* series, is considered the most accomplished and artistically powerful example of Akhundov's prose. It can be stated with confidence that *Qaraca Girl* is the work that brought Akhundov fame and established his reputation as a prose writer. In many respects, this story stands apart from his other prose works.

One of its most notable features is the vivid portrayal of events and characters, the author's direct engagement with life, and the expression of profound humanist ideas in a refined artistic form. There is not a single page in the narrative where the author's compassionate heart and sense of humanity are not felt (8, p.112). A deep appreciation for the beauty of childhood—its value and emotional depth—is expressed more prominently and powerfully in this work than in others.

If the issue of moral upbringing was presented and resolved as a central problem in *Nurəddin*, then in *Qaraca Girl*, Akhundov reveals the essence and qualities of humanism. He identifies the values and sources

that define this humanism. In the story, humanism emerges through a respectful and affectionate portrayal of "ordinary people." A deep love for such individuals lies at the core of Akhundov's educational ideals and represents the most admirable aspect of his humanism (5, p.129).

The story presents the sorrow and bitterness of orphanhood and poverty with emotional impact and accurately identifies the causes behind these conditions. The author contrasts poor, helpless, and modest individuals with the morally corrupt who have grown arrogant through wealth. As expressed in *Qaraca Girl*, Akhundov concludes that, unlike the rich, poor people possess the best qualities, pure intentions, and benevolent aspirations that are essential to a noble human nature. According to Akhundov, the root of all social injustice lies in the desire for wealth and the obsession with material gain. His concern for the fate of the powerless and the vulnerable is a distinctive feature of his humanism (5, p.127).

The story is drawn from the lives of nomadic Roma people. This choice is deliberate. By focusing on individuals who live in partial isolation from society, the author seeks to highlight the contrast that emerges when such individuals encounter the broader world. He emphasizes their loss of spiritual freedom through vivid and expressive detail. As long as Tutu—*Qaraca Girl*—

remains in nature's open embrace, she is cheerful, care-free, and free. The moment she leaves that environment, her days of hardship and suffering begin.

"Qaraca Girl—Tutu, whom the author describes with special affection, is an orphan. Tutu has lost her support and protection—her father and mother. Her misfortunes begin in early childhood. There are few people in her surroundings who recognize her suffering or reflect on her situation. It is no coincidence that although her real name is Tutu, everyone calls her Qaraca Girl. The author, through this name, seems to foreshadow her future filled with tragedy and darkness" (7, p.214).

Despite the injustices she faces in life, Qaraca Girl preserves her purity and the kindness inherent in her nature. The death of her parents, the drowning of Yasaman who had taken her in as a daughter, the cruelty of Yusif, and the deprivation she experiences in Hüseyinqulu Agha's household all put her through severe trials. However, she remains unshaken and continues to live with trust and love toward those around her.

Qaraca Girl encounters various people, each of whom plays a unique role in her life. Yasaman adopts her and cares for her. Yusif causes her pain and suffering. Condemning her husband's unjust treatment of Qaraca Girl, Yasaman says, "... A bear is an animal, but she is a human being. You cannot treat a human the way you treat an animal. If a thick stick is needed for an animal, a human being needs kindness and gentle words" (10, p.324).

Her meeting with Ağca Khanum in Hüseyinqulu Agha's household becomes a turning point in Qaraca Girl's life. Weary of Yusif's cruelty, she believes a new chapter has begun for her and feels joy, looking to the future with hope.

S. S. Akhundov examines the social environment through the eyes of his young protagonist. He reveals injustice and social inequality, and does not conceal his disdain for the ruling class—the "wealthy people." In the author's view, Tutu represents the key measure by which injustice and truth are distinguished. The friends of Qaraca Girl are portrayed with warmth and affection, having earned the author's sympathy. Her enemies, as well as those of the author, are also shown as enemies of the poor and the powerless. Whether the characters are presented in a positive or negative light, the author remains faithful to realism and truth in his depictions. Akhundov structures the narrative around three main periods in Tutu's life, and all other events are connected to these phases.

The first period encompasses Tutu's brief but meaningful and sweet early childhood, a time when she is still happy. During this phase, she is not yet orphaned and has no real sorrows. She thinks and reasons like a child. Tutu fears no one, for she has someone to rely on and a home in which to take shelter. Yet this period ends quickly. Qaraca Girl's life of hardship begins.

The second stage of her life unfolds among the nomadic Roma. Their way of life teaches her many things. Alongside learning to sing, play music, and dance, Tutu also comes to understand that she must endure hardship and deprivation. What sweetens this bitter life, ignites hope in her heart, uplifts her spirit, and fills her with

optimism is her sensitive heart, cheerful childlike nature, and refined taste. Qaraca Girl seems to be a child of nature—of the mountains, the snow, the forests, and the plains. She spends her life in the serene embrace of nature. The wild slopes, steep cliffs, silent dense woods, and roaring waterfalls—places somewhat removed from society—fill her soul with joy and delight, and purify her inner world.

Thanks to this, Qaraca Girl grows up with a sound character, never knowing deceit, manipulation, or selfish intent. Every flower she smells nourishes her soul with its fragrance, leaving its mark on her body and spirit. Whoever recognizes and values the depth of her heart is her true friend, regardless of who they are. At the same time, Qaraca Girl is unwavering and firm in her enmities. This, too, is a noble trait. Only one who can truly hate deeply is also capable of loving deeply. Qaraca Girl is ready to sacrifice herself for her companion or friend, and she remains relentless and unyielding toward her enemy.

Although Qaraca Girl appears "rough" on the outside, she has a gentle and compassionate heart. The writer notes: "Children were afraid of Qaraca Girl. She was very bold, and no one could stand against her fists. Qaraca Girl always took the side of the weak" (8, p.123).

The third stage of Qaraca Girl's life is marked by her days spent in captivity. To imagine this life, we need only close our eyes for a moment and picture the rule of the landlord and nobleman. In this oppressive atmosphere, we find a group of individuals driven by dark intentions: the cruel and merciless Yusif; the selfish and devilish Pəricahan Khanum; the aimless, gluttonous, and lifeless Hüseyinqulu Bey; and the rigid Mariya Ivanovna, whose every action reflects only formality and legalism. Although they come from different backgrounds, their disgraceful behavior unites them. There is only one word to describe these people: savages. Their humanity exists only in name. Their inner world, actions, and character are alike. What they share is a pettiness of spirit, a tendency to look down on others, especially the poor, to insult dignity, and to oppose freedom and independence.

One of those filled with base instincts is Yusif. He torments Qaraca Girl, humiliates her, and is also merciless toward his wife, Yasaman. Yasaman, a noble soul who treats Qaraca Girl with maternal care and ultimately sacrifices her life to protect her, is crushed under the weight of Yusif's cruelty. In general, Yusif is the enemy of all sensitive and compassionate people. He exercises power only over the weak and becomes servile and pathetic in front of the wealthy. His sole objective is to acquire wealth. Both his wife Yasaman and Qaraca Girl serve merely as instruments to this end. But does Yusif want money in order to build a secure future? No, his interest in money lies in pursuing a base life of indulgence and depravity. Yusif is entirely driven by animalistic desires. He treats everyone harshly—whether people or animals under his care. He causes suffering and leaves no one content.

Even Yusif's bear senses his cruelty, along with Qaraca Girl. Though she remains silent due to her powerlessness and isolation, the bear cannot endure the

abuse and mauls Yusif to death. Yusif's death elicits a sense of relief in the reader. The silent and speechless animal's act against such a brutal man is both meaningful and emotionally powerful. Strangely, when the bear is later shot by hunters, the reader cannot help but feel a sense of sorrow.

She is freed from physical torment, but she falls into a far more harrowing condition—spiritual captivity. At this stage, a second obstacle appears in her path: Pəricahan Khanum, the most dangerous enemy of Qaraca Girl and of the poor in general. This woman, who exists entirely as a predator of the oppressed, tramples Qaraca Girl's dignity upon their first encounter. In Pəricahan's behavior and mindset, S. S. Akhundov encapsulates crude and merciless impulses. Hardened by wealth and social status, this shameless woman refuses to recognize anyone. Having turned her husband Hüseynqulu Bey into a mere puppet, she becomes even more depraved and unrestrained. She is ready to sacrifice everything to her personal desires and selfishness. This is a feature rooted in her class nature. She dislikes Qaraca Girl because the girl belongs to a poor social class and possesses both talent and intelligence. Although Pəricahan herself is immersed in moral filth from head to toe, she looks down on everyone and respects no one.

What emboldens Pəricahan is not only her wealth or her husband's submission. She has become accustomed to seeing everyone bow and degrade themselves before her. This habituation has made her intolerant of independence. Any sign of freedom or self-expression offends her deeply. Pəricahan Khanum believes she is acting meaningfully by mimicking the outward elements of culture. She is thoroughly self-satisfied. Although she neither appreciates nor understands knowledge and enlightenment, she insists on educating her daughter. For her, schooling is nothing more than a fashionable trend. The writer subtly points to a deeper truth through this characterization. In her eyes, art and science are simply alternative avenues to profit.

Consequently, Pəricahan Khanum has turned her daughter, Ağca Khanum, who possesses a sincere heart, sound mind, and intellectual potential, into a lifeless figure wrapped in an unnecessary, bizarre, and fashionable garment. This garment not only restricts Ağca Khanum's movements but also suffocates her breath and intensifies her heartbeat. Ağca Khanum longs to tear off this mask of fashion, to dress simply like Qaraca Girl, to be free and independent as she is. However, her governess, the bureaucratic Mariya Ivanovna, does not allow it. Her concern is that if Ağca Khanum gets close to Qaraca Girl, she may lose her "refined" manners, learn too much, and become "corrupted." For Qaraca Girl might pass on her awareness and understanding to Ağca Khanum as well. The young woman's artificial elegance, pretentious customs, and theatrical poses could dissolve. She might become a real person, assert her rights, and choose to live according to her own mind. Pəricahan Khanum's harsh and unjust treatment of her own daughter illustrates with stark realism how a cloud of backwardness attempts to obscure the light of knowledge and reason.

The enemies of Qaraca Girl are also part of the exploiting class that gathers behind the cloud of ignorance. Yet in life, there are also those who value knowledge and understanding, who appreciate talent and courage. These individuals are, above all, the friends of the orphaned Tutu—Qaraca Girl—who, though outwardly "unattractive," possesses inner beauty. These figures include Piri Baba, Ağca Khanum, and Yasaman.

Among them, Yasaman, Ağca Khanum, and Piri Baba serve as her protectors and sources of refuge. These are the positive characters that S. S. Akhundov portrays with a highly realistic and natural touch. Yasaman is bound to Qaraca Girl by maternal feelings. Ağca Khanum is her spiritual companion, while Piri Baba is her loyal ally, her support, and her shelter. Alongside Qaraca Girl, the writer presents the fates, lives, sorrows, and joys of these three individuals in a vivid and emotionally resonant manner.

The bond between Piri Baba and Qaraca Girl is especially meaningful. Piri Baba is a kind and noble old man, created by S. S. Akhundov with inspiration and deep affection. Filled with sincere intentions and compassion, he is a man of clear conscience. His luminous face, dignified character, and benevolent actions command respect. Even Hacı, and Hüseynqulu Bey himself—who holds power over Piri Baba—appear diminished in comparison to his moral stature. As an individual, Piri Baba stands above them all.

Piri Baba is a gardener by profession. Yet there is a sense of greatness and dignity in his craft. Through his sound judgment and generous heart, he has given meaning to his work. Before Qaraca Girl arrives at the nobleman's house, Piri Baba lives in solitude, overcome by pessimism, silently enduring the injustices he perceives. Her arrival changes his life. It is as if Qaraca Girl becomes a healing balm for his wounded heart. He casts off the weight of loneliness. With her presence, Qaraca Girl brings new life and new light to this aging, childless man's old hut. His dark room becomes illuminated. From the silence that once echoed like a grave, the promise of new life begins to resound.

Qaraca Girl gives her life in the name of friendship. Even in her final breath, she dies with a pure intention. Sacrificing herself to save the life of her childhood companion and confidante, Ağca Khanum, Qaraca Girl perishes. Alongside Piri Baba, who openly protests against the injustice, the reader also raises their voice in protest, expressing firm opposition to the "world of the noblemen" that caused her death.

The work is also distinguished by its artistic merit. Built on a cohesive composition and marked by a consistent plot structure, the events in the story develop in a connected and logical sequence. These qualities contribute to its engaging and enjoyable narrative. The author's language, use of imagery, and particularly the vivid portrayal of natural scenes enrich the literary form of the story.

The author skillfully connects the internal world, thoughts, and actions of his characters with elements of the natural environment. Nature is not described merely for aesthetic purposes. "The flow of events, the nature-

reflecting scenes, and the unfolding action serve as artistic devices that help readers grasp the emotional states and conditions of the characters.” (14, p.89). Throughout the fluid and clear narrative, we hear the joyful beating of human hearts, the voice of rage against injustice, and the words of sorrow shaped by suffering.

The ending of the story stands out for the realism and completeness of its final scene. It is a powerful and emotionally resonant moment, one that leaves a lasting impression and remains vivid in memory. This scene may rightly be called one of sorrow and tears.

"*Qaraca Girl* is a true artistic gem, distinguished by its unique literary, social, moral, and aesthetic value, even when compared with examples from classic European and Russian children's literature," as noted by literary scholars and researchers of S. Sani's work. This assessment is well justified (10, pp.13–14).

Although the style and tone of the story resemble that of folk tales, the events depicted in the narrative are based on real-life occurrences. The work offers an artistic portrayal of the contradictions within society, various human characters and destinies, and the nature of social relationships.

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